

**UTILIZING *MUSHĀRAKAH MUTANĀQISAH*
PARTNERSHIP FOR MICRO AND MEDIUM
ENTERPRISES (MMES)**

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Bay' bithaman al-ājil and murābahah are the two instruments most commonly used by Islamic banks and financial institutions. Investment and financing through the profit and loss sharing (PLS) instruments is almost nonexistent in the total financing of Islamic financial system. Mushārahah mutanāqisah partnership (MMP) technique is an alternative financial instrument available for Islamic banks. This technique entails both partnership and leasing features. It enables a more efficient way of acquiring necessary assets for client and, at the same time, solves the liquidity problem faced by the financial institutions. The MMP financial technique is widely used for home purchase but its applicability goes beyond this limited scope. In this paper we are proposing this technique for financing micro and medium enterprises (MMEs). We believe that by implementing this mechanism it would help develop MME sector which will bring about overall economic development. This model has great advantages over those widely used instrument, but it also bears some disadvantages that has to be addressed.

1. INTRODUCTION

For proper development of an economy it is very important that every sector within that economy is well organized and functions as efficiently as possible. Micro and medium enterprises (MMEs) are integral part of every economy and they are playing an important role in economic development. Therefore the due attention should be paid to this sector in order to facilitate its development which will, further on, lead to the general economic prosperity.

According to the *Shari'ah* teachings, the receipt and payment of the interest (*riba*) is prohibited (Qur'an, *al-Baqarah*: 275). Consequently, the financing of the projects, business activities or any other financing based on

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riba is not allowed by *Shari'ah*. Therefore, the Muslim entrepreneurs should be provided with the *Shari'ah* based¹ financing mechanisms. Since the *riba* and *riba*-based financing are prohibited in Islam, the *Shari'ah* provided alternative option which is trade. Allah (s.w.t.) says: "... Allah hath permitted trade and forbidden usury..." (Qur'an, *al-Baqarah*: 275). The trade is not only permitted, but rather it is encouraged by the Holy Prophet (pbuh). Al-Suyūṭī, in his book *Al-Jāmi' Al-Saghīr*, mentioned a *hadīth* on the authority of Rāfi' that: "The Prophet (pbuh) was asked: "which are the best forms of income generation?" He (pbuh) replied: "A man's labor, and every legitimate sale" (Cited in El Gemal, 2000). Muslim scholars are unanimous that Islamic banking and finance should be primarily based on profit and loss sharing (PLS) mechanism and not through interest (i.e. fixed excess return for a fixed amount for a determined period of time, or any excess exchange of similar commodity) (Islam, 2006). Furthermore, *Qur'an* talks about cooperation among Muslims in good deeds and avoiding bad ones by saying:

يَتَأْتِيهَا الَّذِينَ ءَامَنُوا لَا تَحْلُوا شَعْتِرَ اللَّهِ وَلَا الشَّهْرَ الْحَرَامَ وَلَا الْهَدْيَ
وَلَا الْقَلْبِدَ وَلَا ءَامِينَ الْبَيْتِ الْحَرَامِ يَبْتَغُونَ فَضْلًا مِّن رَّبِّهِمْ وَرِضْوَانًا
وَإِذَا حَلَلْتُمْ فَاصْطَادُوا وَلَا يَجْرِمَنَّكُمْ شَتَانُ قَوْمٍ أَن صَدُّوكُمْ عَنِ
الْمَسْجِدِ الْحَرَامِ أَن تَعْتَدُوا وَتَعَاوَنُوا عَلَى الْبِرِّ وَالتَّقْوَىٰ وَلَا تَعَاوَنُوا
عَلَى الْإِثْمِ وَالْعُدْوَانِ وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ إِنَّ اللَّهَ شَدِيدُ الْعِقَابِ ﴿٢٠٦﴾

"O ye who believe! violate not the sanctity of the Symbols of Allah nor of the Sacred Month nor of the animals brought for sacrifice nor the garlands that mark out such animals nor the people resorting to the Sacred House seeking of the bounty and good pleasure of their Lord. But when ye are clear of the Sacred Precincts and of pilgrim garb ye may hunt and let not the hatred of some people in (once) shutting you out of the Sacred Mosque lead you to transgression (and hostility on your part). Help ye one another in

¹ Here, the author purposely uses this terminology to stress the attention on the *Shari'ah* validity of Islamic instruments mostly used by the Islamic banks nowadays.

righteousness and piety but help ye not one another in sin and rancor: fear Allah: for Allah is strict in punishment." (Al-Qur'an, al-Mā'idah: 2).

This cooperation has been promoted and implemented by the Holy Prophet (p.b.u.h) between *Ansārs* and *Muhājirūn* in Madinah. *Mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership (MMP) is a direct result and implementation of the above verses. MMP or partnership culminating in ownership is an innovative instrument in Islamic banking industry. It could be considered as a derivative of original *mushārahah*, *ijārah* and *bay'ah* modes of financing. Here, these three modes of finance are combined in order to facilitate asset acquisition or project financing. MMP consists of two portions (Meera and Dzuljastri, 2005). First one consists of *mushārahah* (partnership) between the customer and the bank. This is done through the contract of '*Shirkat-al-Milik*'. For example, the customer and the bank invest in the project with initial capital investment equals 20% and 80% by them respectively. The customer will continue to buy the shares of the bank gradually until the project is fully owned by him. Second portion is implemented through the contract of *ijārah* between the customer and bank. Here, the customer rents the bank's shares in the project (i.e. land, premises, etc.) from the bank and pays the rental payment, which is shared between the two based on their percentage of shares. Slowly, the shares of the customer will increase while the shares of the bank will decrease, through the periodical redemption by the customer, until the project is fully owned by the customer.

This paper is divided into five sections, including introduction. Second section is literature review. Here the main literature on the topic is reviewed and highlighted. Third section is the overview of the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership. The definitions, legality, classifications and profit and loss issues are all discussed here. This section also explains the mechanism of *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership and how it can be implemented using an appropriate example. Mathematical derivation that is used to calculate monthly rental payment and additional payment due by a customer is the subject matter of the section four. Finally, section five is left for the concluding remarks on the MMP model presented in this paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The *mushārahah mutanāqisah* or diminishing partnership is relatively a new financing technique available to the Islamic banks. Even though the mechanism of *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership has been

approved by the First International Conference on Islamic Banking, held in Dubai in 1979 (Bendjilali and Khan, 1995: 16), it has not been widely implemented throughout Islamic financial system. In this section, we will try to review available literature on *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership and give readers necessary background on the topic.

Many problems have been raised about the inability of Islamic banks in implementing traditional *mudhārahah* and *mushārahah* (hereinafter referred to as M-M) modes of financing with regard to their complexity, agency problem (Obiyathullah, 2006), trustworthiness, duration and termination of the contract etc. In that regard, Bendjilali and Khan (1995) are of opinion that termination of financier's ownership in certain economic activities is a necessity. Another paper by Khan (1995) is also addressing the issue of redeemability of M-M modes of financing. It goes on by saying that pure *mudhārahah* funds are not redeemable. Traditional modes of financing (i.e. M-M) do not offer such option. This non-terminating nature of M-M "imposes limitations on the provision of bank finance to newer projects and entrepreneurial activities" (Bendjilali and Khan, 1995: 14). In this regard Bendjilali and Khan (1995) propose the use of *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership (MMP) as it enables financier to gradually terminate his/her ownership in a project. They argue that some of the problems faced by M-M could be avoided through implementation of MMP. For example, it is expected that partial ownership of the project could be a fair deterrent against moral hazards. At the same time, as the capital share of a bank gradually decreases in a given project, its cash flow improves and recovered capital, together with its share of profits, could be used for investment in new projects.

Rosly (2005) is of opinion that MMP is one possible solution to the volatility and uncertainty faced by Islamic banks due to their overdependence on BBA financing technique (referring to the case of Malaysia and Bank Negara's proposal for a floating rate option). The objective of the MMP is to earn a profits through the investment, while the object of the investment – he says – is to own a property. Capital contribution by the partners is not fixed and can vary from contract to contract. However, more research is necessary in order for this contract to get wide acceptance by public – according to Rosly. We hope that this research can help in this regard.

It is believed that MMP, as a mode of Islamic financing, is both efficient and equitable at the same time (Bendjilali and Khan, 1995: 55). Under the MMP, the period needed for the transfer of ownership will be shorter (Bendjilali and Khan, 1995: 54 and Meera and Dzuljastri, 20). Furthermore, Bendjilali and Khan (1995) opine that MMP could lead to specialization, productivity and alleviation of poverty through redistribution mechanism. In addition to that, MMP is also proposed by Rosly (2005) as a solution to the market volatility and uncertainty.

The *mushārahah mutanāqisah* financing technique was one of the modes for house financing discussed and approved during the workshop organized by Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), Jeddah, and Sudanese Estates Bank, Sudan, held in Khartoum in 1991 (Mahdi, 1995). Several papers have been presented in which various techniques have been explained for house financing. Application of these modes by several institutions, such as Jordan Islamic Bank and Al-Baraka International Bank London, are elaborated and explained. Participants of the workshop concluded that the *mushārahah mutanāqisah*, among other modes of financing, is allowed by *Shari'ah* and can be implemented in house financing. The main objections to this mode of finance were: firstly regarding the construction of the contract; and secondly the determination of the price of the shares. It is agreed that it is not allowed to have more than one contract in a single contract where a contract may represent a condition to another contract. It is also believed that the share prices should be determined in accordance with market forces.

Meera and Dzuljastri (2005) compared *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership with conventional loans and BBA financing facility. They showed that out of these three, MMP is the most efficient in terms of cost incurred by a client. In other words, MMP is relatively the most affordable mode of financing. In addition to that, the duration of financing could be substantially lowered. It is interesting to note that the balance, at any point of time, would not exceed the original amount extended by the financier.

Both, MMP and conventional loans, follow diminishing balance method and therefore the balance, at any point of time, cannot exceed the original amount. On the other hand, balance under BBA facility can be higher than initial contribution by the financier. Being less expensive for the clients compared to BBA, MMP – the authors argued – may not be attractive to the banks since this may reduce their earnings. Due to that, the

authors suggested its implementation through cooperatives where the funds are provided by the members for the members. Furthermore, the advantage of cooperatives lies in the fact that there will be no money creation as is the case with fractional reserve banking. This will further promote the objectives of *Shari'ah* (*maqāsid al-Shari'ah*). However, MMP is far from being perfect. There are operational problems, such as determination of rental rate, taxation, land laws, etc., that need to be addressed in depth. One of the suggestions is to use Rental Index or House Price Index to avoid any linkage to interest rate.

3. OVERVIEW OF MUSHĀRAKAH

Mushārahah represents the partnership whereby the partners share the profit according to agreed ratio/proportion, while the loss is in proportion to the capital invested by the partners. This principle was firstly introduced by Quraishi in his work *Islam and the Theory of Interest*. However, it was formally discussed by Ahmad in *Economics of Islam*, in 1947 (See Kahf and Khan, 1992: 24). Since general *mushārahah* is covered well in the literature we will avoid it here and focus more on the issues related to the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership.

3.1 Definition

Bendjilali and Khan (1995) define *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership or *mushārahah yantahī bi al-tamlīk* (partnership which ends in transferring of ownership to one party - the client) as a diminishing partnership whereby a product/project becomes fully owned by a client. It is a combination of sale and sharing contracts whereby the ownership is transferred through sale and this transfer is done through profit sharing arrangement.

3.2 Legality of *mushārahah mutanāqisah*

Shari'ah validity of general *mushārahah* contract can be found in the *Qur'an* (for example see *an-Nisa'*: 12 and *Sād*: 23-24), the Prophet's *Sunnah* and consensus of Muslim scholars (*ijma'*).

When it comes to the legality of the *mushāraka mutanāqisah* partnership model, then we can say that it is fully in line with *Shari'ah*. It consists of several contracts, namely *mushāraka* (partnership), *ijārah*

(leasing) and *bay'* (sale), whose validity is found in all sources of *Shari'ah*. There is no disagreement even among the Muslim scholars on its permissibility. The only slight differences exist with regard to the conditions related to the MMP and its implementation.

It should be also noted that the *mushāraka mutanāqisah* partnership has been discussed and agreed upon even during the first Islamic Banking conference held in Dubai 23-25 of *Jumad Thani* 1399H (1979) (Abdallah, 1995: 48).

3.3 Profit and loss sharing under *mushārah mutanāqisah*

It is important to note that in a cooperative agreement such as *mushārah*, partners mingle their capitals and make it as one that is indistinguishable. All the partners in *mushārah* can participate in managing funds, but if a partner does not want to take a part in management it is still a valid partnership. This means that participating in management under *mushārah* contract is not required. The same applies to the *mushāraka mutanāqisah* partnership.

Regarding the profit and loss sharing, partners must agree at the beginning of a partnership on an exact proportion of the profit that is due to each one of them. *Shari'ah* did not prescribe any specific proportion, rather it is up to the partners to agree on. It can be in equal proportions or in different ones. The only thing that *Shari'ah* does not allow is to prescribe a lump-sum amount of profit for any party involved in partnership or any percentage tied up with the capital (Usmani, 2002 and AAOIFI, 2004). However, the partners are free to agree on any percentage of the profit to be allocated between them.

On the other hand, Muslim scholars are unanimous about the sharing of the loss incurred in *mushārah*. In this case they all agree that it *must* be according to the capital invested by each party involved. For example, if the financier's and the client's shares in *mushārah* are in proportion 40:60 then the loss will be borne in that vary same proportion, i.e. 40:60 respectively.

3.4 Termination of *mushārahah mutanāqisah*

It is generally agreed that the *mushāraka*, in general, and therefore *mushāraka mutanāqisah*, in particular, can be terminated at any time by any party involved. In other words, this is not binding contract and every partner can quit or sell his/her shares to others. The only situation when a partner is not allowed to sell his/her shares is in the case when it can hurt the other side, i.e. his/her partner (Siraj, 1998).

3.5 Mechanism and basic conditions of valid MMP

The *mushāraka mutanāqisah* or decreasing partnership represents a joint venture between the bank and the customer where they jointly purchase the property (house, car, machinery or any other asset). Once acquired, the property is leased to the customer who pays the rent to the bank for using its shares in the property. Together with the rent, the customer will pay additional amount in order to redeem the shares of the financier. Consequently the financier's shares will decrease while the customer's shares will increase until the property is fully owned by the customer. This mechanism entails three contracts – according to Usmani (1995: 67-68). These contracts are:

- i) Establishment of the joint venture;
- ii) Leasing the shares of financier to the customer; and
- iii) Selling the successive shares of the financier to the customer.

The *mushāraka mutanāqisah* model can be easily implemented for a various financing purposes. It has been mostly used for home financing. However, this model can be easily implemented for any other financing needs. This model would provide a great opportunity for micro and medium enterprise entities that are in dire need for capital for running day-to-day activities. To illustrate how MMP financing technique could be implemented, consider the following example for instance:

Ahmad wants to start a factory that produces home furniture, but he lacks necessary funds for running that business. Let us assume that for starting this business Ahmad needs RM200,000. He approaches the bank and asks for assistance. The bank enters into joint venture with Ahmad whereby the bank finances 90% of the necessary capital (RM180,000),

while the remaining 10% (RM20,000) is financed by Ahmad himself. There are two scenarios that could be implemented here:

(i) *Profit and loss sharing:* Once Ahmad starts operating and earns income that will be divided according to agreed ratio. Accordingly that if the agreed ratio is 80:20 for the bank and Ahmad respectively, then 80% of the profit would go to the bank and 20% to Ahmad. It should be noted that this ratio may be in the same proportion as their capital contribution or it may be different one. However, if loss occurs then it will be shared according to capital contribution only. Islamic scholars are unanimous on this.

The bank's share in the business will be further divided into equal units, each representing additional shares in the business. Ahmad agrees that he will buy additional unit of the shares after an agreed period of time. Consequently, Ahmad will buy additional shares of the business and his shares in the business will increase while decreasing the shares of the bank. Following this method, Ahmad will completely own the business after an agreed period (it can be any amount of years). Using this mechanism, the bank earns periodical profits generated out of the business plus it regains the original amount invested in the business through the periodical sale of its shares to Ahmad.

(ii) *Renting the premises:* The above-mentioned example is one way of operating under MMP model. The other one would be if the bank and Ahmad enter the joint venture and Ahmed starts the business while paying the rent to the bank for using its shares in the business. If we assume that the rental in that area is RM2,000 per month, this is the amount to be shared between the parties according to their capital contribution. This means that out of RM2,000, RM1,800 and RM200 will go to the bank and Ahmad respectively. Ahmad may add up additional amount of money in order to speed up the buy-back of the shares from the bank. Once Ahmad buys additional units of shares from the bank, his shares will rise, causing the shares of the bank to decrease. In the same way the share in the rental payment will be adjusted, until the business is fully owned by Ahmad and no rental is paid to the bank. Following this scenario, the bank will earn the rent throughout the period plus it will regain its original capital invested in the joint venture. This example will be further substantiated by the mathematical model later on in this paper.

As we can see from the above examples, the *mushāraka mutanāqisah* partnership can be easily used for any financial purposes while adhering to the basic tenets of the *Shari'ah*, such as avoiding interest. It is obvious from the above that *mushāraka mutanāqisah* financing technique consists of three parts, namely: *mushāraka* (partnership), *ijārah* (leasing) and *bay'* (sale). All of these contracts are allowed by *Shari'ah* and consensus of the *'ulamā*. However, some issues arise when it comes to combining of these three contracts under one. It is general agreement of the Muslim scholars that two contracts combined into one, where one of them is conditional for another, is not allowed by *Shari'ah*. Therefore, *'ulamā* put forward several conditions for this mode of finance to be valid from *Shari'ah* point of view. These conditions are summarized by Muhammad Taqi Usmani (2002: 31-34) as follows:

1. Creating a joint ownership in the property (*Shirkat-al-Milk*): This creation of *Shirkat-al-Milk* is allowed by all schools of Islamic jurisprudence.
2. Leasing of the financier's shares to the client: There is also no difference of opinion among the Muslim jurists when it comes to the permissibility of leasing one's undivided shares in a property to his/her partner. However, if the shares are leased out to the third party then there is a difference of opinion in its permissibility among the Muslim jurists.
3. The client's promise to buy the financier's shares: Islam does not allow the combination of several transactions into one contract or making one transaction a condition to another. However, instead of making two transactions conditional to each other, the jurists suggest a one-sided promise; in our case this promise should come from the client in form that he is going to lease the financier's share in capital and pay agreed rent, plus to purchase the financier's shares at different stages throughout the agreed period. Here the question of enforceability of promise comes into the picture. Some would say that the promise is only a moral obligation without legal enforcement. On the other hand, it is believed that this promise is not only a moral obligation but also it is a right of original seller that can be enforced by the law. This is based on the principle that: "قد تجعل المواعيد لازمة لحاجة الناس" –

"*The promise can be made enforceable at the time of need*" (Usmani, 2002: 33).²

4. Actual purchase of the shares: The sale of the shares by the financier to the client must be effected through the offer and acceptance on that particular date. In addition to that, it is also preferable that this sale is carried out based on the market value of the shares at the time of the sale of any particular share/unit. However, it is also permissible for the price to be agreed in the contract (Usmani, 2002).
5. Rental adjustment according to the remaining shares of the financier: After every buy-back of the financier's shares by the client, the share ratio will be altered and at the same time the rental will be changed proportionally.

Apart from the conditions put forward by Usmani, the following has been suggested by Bendjilali and Khan (1995: 17-19): a) There should be promise by the bank to put its shares on sale at specific future date; b) The purchase of the shares should not be binding on the customer; and c) The prices should be determined at the time of sale.

The only issue at question here is regarding the determination of the prices of the different units of the financier's shares. Usmani (2002) is of opinion that these prices can be agreed in the promise signed by the client, but he gives preference to the market determination of the price of shares. However, Bendjilali and Khan (1995) opine that it should be at the market value. This is also upheld by the AAOIFI standards. AAOIFI states that to acquire the shares at their original or face value is not allowed to be stipulated (i.e. predetermined), since this would guarantee the value of the shares of one partner by the other partner and this is against *Shari'ah* (2004: 214-215). *Shaykh* al-Darir is of the same opinion as stated earlier. Therefore, it can be concluded that the prices of shares should be determined through market forces.

² Here, the *italics* are ours for emphasis.

3.6 Salient features of the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership³

Bendjilali and Khan (1995) listed down the following salient features of the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership. They are as follows:

- i) Creation of joint-venture between the client and the bank on the basis of *mushārahah*.
- ii) Profits are to be shared in accordance to the agreed ratio, but the losses are to be shared in proportion of capital invested by each party involved.
- iii) There should be unilateral, binding promise by the financier to sell his shares of the partnership on installments.
- iv) The client voluntarily buys the shares of the financier which are to be priced at the market value at the time of the sale.
- v) The sale component of MMP contract is binding only on the financier.

3.7 Advantages and disadvantages of the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership

There are several advantages as well as disadvantages in implementing the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership. We will briefly explain some of them in the following lines.

3.7.1 Advantages of the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership

Some of the advantages listed below are discussed by Meera and Dzuljastri (2005). They are as follows:

- (i) It is a cheaper mode of finance for asset acquisition, at least from a customer's point of view, than asset financing through either BBA mode of financing or conventional loan. Furthermore, BBA financing puts extra pressure on the customer and causes hardship for him/her.
- (ii) The period for financing can be also shortened which would be beneficial for both the bank and the client. The former will receive the funds invested which could be reinvested

³ I fully acknowledge indebtedness to Bendjilali and Khan for this subtitle. See: Bendjilali and Khan, *Economics of Diminishing Musharakah*, 19-20.

into new projects. The latter will be able to acquire the needed asset in shorter period of time. This shows that MMP is, as compared to BBA, relatively more flexible mode of financing.

- (iii) The financing and the payment of the installments as well as the rent can be adjusted periodically to reflect the market changes. This makes the *mushāraka mutanāqisah* partnership less vulnerable to the outside factors such as the movements in interest rate and inflation faced by other alternatives (i.e. BBA financing and conventional loans). It also gives financier better option for managing liquidity risks.
- (iv) It is in line with *maqāsid al-Shari'ah* which promotes *maslahah*, the welfare of the people, by making it easier for them, the clients, to finance their asset acquisitions. It removes the hardship from the people and serves public interest which is desirable.
- (v) Using the *mushāraka mutanāqisah* partnership model, the interest (*ribā*) can be avoided totally which makes this model more *Islamic* than BBA which is debt based mode of finance.
- (vi) Under this model the balance of payment, at any point of time, will never exceed the original price of the asset. This is not the case with BBA.
- (vii) If implemented through cooperatives or mutual funds, this model can have a substantial impact on economy while reducing inflation since there will be no creation of money as is the case under fractional reserve banking system.
- (viii) The selling price, under MMP, always reflects market price and the rental payments are determined through market forces, while in case of BBA the mark-up price is a way above the market price (i.e. it does not reflect the market price of the asset).
- (ix) In case of defaults, under BBA financing technique, Islamic banks are not allowed to charge any penalty (theoretically). This can be avoided in case of MMP mode of finance. Here, in case of default the financier (i.e. the bank) will be entitled to receive higher rental payment since its share in property will remain until the customer resume payments later on. It is believed that this rent may have "a deterrent impact on a

customer who evades repayment as it will remain fixed as long as no repayment of the principal takes place" (Salama, 1995: 32). In case that the customer cannot pay even rent, then the property could be leased to the third party while the profit will be shared between the bank and the customer.

- (x) We have seen that in case of inflation the BBA financing is adversely affected. *Mushāraka* financing guards the financial institution from the bad effects of inflation. Therefore, from the point of view of financial institutions, *mushāraka* financing technique stands better than BBA, *murābaha* or conventional loan since the financial institutions can secure a percentage of the value of the asset. This way when the asset appreciates with inflation, the shares of the financial institutions appreciate as well. Furthermore, if the asset is sold, the financial institutions' share will increase as result of capital appreciation (Salama, 1995: 31-32).

3.7.2 Disadvantages of the *mushārakah mutanāqisah* partnership

- (i) It is less attractive for the banks since under the *mushāraka mutanāqisah* partnership would bring lower profits to the Islamic banks. By using BBA mode of finance Islamic banks earn higher profits with less risk and efforts invested in the projects.
However, following basic economic theories, as the price of the products/services decreases (in this case MMP mode of financing) the demand for that service would increase. Therefore, while the banks may lose some profits by implementing MMP, compared to the BBA financing, it will gain some extra profits and therefore offset some of that loss, by initial increase in demand for their services (i.e. MMP).⁴
- (ii) Since the rental price do change over the time and is dictated by the location of the property (in case of home financing) keeping the track of these changes may not be an

⁴ This is only theoretical explanation and the empirical studies should be carried out in order to substantiate this claim. Due to the lack of the data and empirical studies on the topic the author is not able to confirm this claim fully.

easy job for the banks. At the same time, as the rental rate increase it may be difficult for the bank to convince the customer that now he/she has to pay higher rent on the property.

- (iii) Legal amendments may be needed especially in regards to the tax on the properties. This means that the law should be there to make sure that the customer is not taxed twice for the same property.
- (iv) Land laws and the laws related to the Islamic banking and finance (i.e. Islamic Banking Act [IBA] 1983 and the Banking and Financial Institutions Act 1989 [BAFIA] in case of Malaysia) may have to be amended in order to facilitate this mechanism.

3.8 Examples of MMP being practiced by some institutions worldwide for home financing

The *mushāraka mutanāqisah* partnership has been implemented by many Islamic financial institutions throughout the world. Usually the MMP model is used for house financing, as we stated earlier, but this model can be used for any other business purposes especially for MMEs. In this section we will highlight and elaborate some of these institutions and their practices.

There are two cooperative financial houses in Canada operating on the principle of *mushāraka mutanāqisah* partnership. They are Islamic Co-operative Housing Corporation (ICHC) and Ansar Co-operative Housing Corporation (ACHC), both based in Toronto and established in 1981. The purpose of setting up these Co-operatives was to help Muslims in Canada to buy a home without paying interest or mortgage. To become a member of Co-operative, an individual is required to buy shares of the Co-operative. In order to be entitled to get financing from the Co-operative a member needs to have shares equal to 10% of his/her outstanding mortgage balance as an investment in the Co-operative for at least six months. Once a member meets this requirement, the Co-operative will buy a house for this member to live, while paying fair and mutually agreed occupancy charges (i.e. rent). This rent is proportionate to the Co-operative's ownership in the house. At the same time, the members are required to buy more shares in Co-operative so that their ownership shares will increase. As the shares of members in Co-operative increases the rent will decrease proportionally, until the house

great potential.⁵ Some of the institutions, besides the above-mentioned, which offer Islamic mortgage, are Ahli United Bank, West Bromwich Building Society, United National Bank and the Islamic Bank of Britain.

American Finance House LARIBA (AFHL) is another example of successful implementation of *Shari'ah* modes of finance in US. AFHL is based in Pasadena, California. Its home financing model is based on "Lease-To-Purchase" (LTP) (*ijārah wa iqtinā/diminishing mushārakah*) concept. According to this model, AFHL and the client would purchase the property together. AFHL agrees to sell its shares/units to the client, while the client agrees to re-purchase these shares/units. In this regard, AFHL allows the client to buy the property directly from the vendor and register it under his/her name. The client leases the AFHL's shares in the property and gradually repurchases its shares. The property is leased at market value which is defined by the location and specification of the property and mutually agreed between the AFHL and client. This rent value is divided between two of them in accordance with their proportion of their shares/units of the purchase price of the property. The additional amount is paid by the customer as installment for buying back the shares/units of AFHL. Gradually, the client's shares in the property increases while the AFHL's shares diminish with each installment, until the end of the financing period when the client will own 100% of the shares in the property.⁶

This and similar models are also available in other financial institution in US, Pakistan, Australia, etc. Another example of Muslim community, implementing Declining Balance Co-ownership Program in US, is the case of Guidance Financial Group. In Pakistan, Meezan Bank developed a scheme called "Easy Home" that was the first Islamic home financing facility. This scheme also follows the *mushāraka mutanāqisah* concept of financing. In Australia the similar model is applied through Muslim Community Cooperative (Australia), better known as MCCA. It

⁵ Datamonitor Plc. (UK), *UK Islamic Mortgages 2005*, available at: <URL: <http://www.datamonitor.com>>.

⁶ American Finance House offers Islamic products to finance homes, autos, small business, home renovation, etc. in the following states Alabama, Alaska, Arkansas, California, Colorado, Connecticut, Florida, Georgia, Hawaii, Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Kansas, Kentucky, Louisiana, Maryland, Massachusetts, Michigan, Minnesota, Mississippi, Missouri, Nebraska, Nevada, New Jersey, New Mexico, North Carolina, Oklahoma, Ohio, Oregon, South Carolina, Tennessee, Texas, Virginia, Washington State, Wisconsin and Wyoming.

was found in 1989 with the aim of providing a practical model of Islamic finance in Australia. Their home financing is carried out through *murābaha* and *ijāra muntahia bittamlik*.

These models are also practiced all over the world. Some of the examples are also shown in the boxes provided. It is worth noting here that these models are not applied to the house financing only, rather they are being used in order to finance other asset acquisition as well. For example, it has been used for equipment financing, auto or car financing, business financing, etc. In fact, as stated by Obaidullah (2005: 64), *mushāraka* in general and *mushāraka mutanāqisah* partnership in particular are suitable for financing almost every kind of business ventures, be it manufacturing, trading or any other business where the bank is willing to become a partner.

4. A MATHEMATICAL DERIVATION MODEL

In order for us to calculate necessary installment and rental fees for *mushāraka mutanāqisah* partnership we need a mathematical model. Here we will use the model provided by Kameel and Dzuljastri (2005).

4.1 Model by Kameel and Dzuljastri⁷

P = Price of asset, e.g. a home, car

B_0 = Financier's contribution into the partnership

C_0 = Customer's contribution into the partnership

Therefore the price would be, $P = B_0 + C_0$

R = Periodic rental, eg. monthly

A = Additional periodic payment by customer to redeem the financier's equity faster

$M = R + A$, is therefore, the total periodic payment

Let C_i = the customer's equity (ownership) of the asset in period i

⁷ Note: This is the reproduced mathematical derivation note provided by Meera and Dzuljastri in their paper on "Islamic Home Financing through *Mushāraka Mutanāqisah* and *al-Bay' Bithaman Ajil* Contracts: A Comparative Analysis", *Review of Islamic Economics*, vol. 9, no. 2 (2005): 26-30. The author acknowledges his full indebtedness to this paper.

Let the proportion of customer's equity in period i , $r_i = \frac{C_i}{P}$

Therefore,

$$C_0 = C_0$$

$$C_1 = C_0 + r_0R + A$$

$$C_2 = C_1 + r_1R + A$$

$$C_3 = C_2 + r_2R + A$$

$$C_n = C_{n-1} + r_{n-1}R + A$$

Therefore,

$$C_0 = C_0$$

$$C_1 = C_0 + r_0R + A$$

$$C_2 = C_0 + r_0R + A + r_1R + A = C_0 + R(r_0 + r_1) + 2A$$

$$C_3 = C_0 + r_0R + A + r_1R + A + r_2R + A = C_0 + R(r_0 + r_1 + r_2) + 3A$$

$$C_n = C_0 + R(r_0 + r_1 + r_2 + \dots + r_{n-1}) + nA$$

$$C_n = C_0 + \frac{R}{P}(C_0 + C_1 + C_2 + \dots + C_{n-1}) + nA \quad \text{Since } r_i = \frac{C_i}{P}$$

Let $x = \frac{R}{P}$, then

$$C_1 = C_0 + xC_0 + A = (1+x)C_0 + A$$

$$C_2 = C_0 + x(C_0 + C_0 + xC_0 + A) + 2A = (1+2x+x^2)C_0 + (x+2)A$$

$$C_3 = C_0 + x(C_0 + C_0 + xC_0 + A + C_0 + (C_0 + C_0 + xC_0 + A) + 2A) + 3A \\ = (1+3x+3x^2+x^3)C_0 + (x^2+3x+3)A$$

Therefore,

$$C_1 = (1+x)C_0 + A$$

$$C_2 = (1+x)^2C_0 + (x+2)A$$

$$C_3 = (1+x)^3C_0 + (x^2+3x+3)A$$

$$C_4 = (1+x)^4C_0 + (x^3+4x^2+6x+4)A$$

$$C_n = (1+x)^n C_0 + \left[\frac{(1+x)^n - 1}{x} \right] A \quad (1)$$

and, of course, the proportion of the customer's equity in the n^{th} period is

$$r_n = \frac{C_n}{P}$$

Rewriting equation (1), the number of periods taken by the customer to fully own the house is given by, where $C_n = P$,

$$\begin{aligned} P &= (1+x)^n C_0 + \frac{(1+x)^n}{x} A - \frac{1}{x} A \\ &= (1+x)^n \left[C_0 + \frac{A}{x} \right] - \frac{1}{x} A \\ (1+x)^n &= \frac{P + \frac{A}{x}}{C_0 + \frac{A}{x}} \\ \Rightarrow n &= \frac{\ln\left(P + \frac{A}{x}\right) - \ln\left(C_0 + \frac{A}{x}\right)}{\ln(1+x)} \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

Once the rental, R , has been determined and the customer has decided on the period of partnership, i.e. the n , then the periodic amount the customer has to top up additionally is given by

$$A = \frac{x[P - (1+x)^n C_0]}{(1+x)^n - 1} \quad (3)$$

and, the formula for determining the periodic payment is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 M &= R + A \\
 &= \frac{R[(1+x)^n - 1] + x[P - (1+x)^n C_0]}{(1+x)^n - 1} \\
 &= \frac{R(1+x)^n - R + xP - x(1+x)^n C_0}{(1+x)^n - 1} \\
 &= \frac{x(1+x)^n P - R + R - x(1+x)^n C_0}{(1+x)^n - 1} \quad \text{Since } xP = R \\
 &= \frac{x(1+x)^n [P - C_0]}{(1+x)^n - 1} \\
 &= \frac{x(1+x)^n B_0}{(1+x)^n - 1} \\
 \Rightarrow M &= \frac{x(1+x)^n B_0}{(1+x)^n - 1} \tag{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

which, interestingly, is similar to the normal annuity formula used for computing the payment in conventional loan calculations⁸. Hence, mathematically, the normal annuity formula can also be used for *Mushārah Mutanāqisah* calculations, but the periodic interest rate is replaced by the rental rate, $x = \frac{R}{P}$. Indeed then, the periodic rate of return for *Mushārah Mutanāqisah* Partnership is solely determined by the rental rate, $x = \frac{R}{P}$. Therefore, the

$$\text{Internal Rate of Return (IRR) to bank} = \frac{R}{P} \tag{5}$$

Also,

$$\text{Total payment made to financier} = Mn \tag{6}$$

⁸ Computed using the standard formula for present value of annuities, i.e.

$$PV = \frac{Pmt}{i} \left[1 - \frac{1}{(1+i)^n} \right] \text{ which gives } Pmt = \frac{i(1+i)^n PV}{(1+i)^n - 1}$$

$$\text{Total profit to financier} = Mn - B_0 \quad (7)$$

Note: Since the rate of return (IRR) for the financier is solely determined by the rental rate, $x = \frac{R}{P}$, **irrespective** of the initial capital provided by the financier (B_0) and/or the duration of the partnership (n), the financier may be tempt **to finance only homes with high rental values**; while it is in the interest of the customers to negotiate for low rentals. At the extreme, if the rental is nil, then the *Mushārahah Mutanākisah* financing will become similar to *Qard al-Hassan*.

To illustrate this formula we will use the example mentioned above where Ahmad wants to star the business, producing furniture, for which he needs RM200,000. He is willing and able to invest RM20,000 and asks the banks to form joint venture with him by investing the remaining RM180,000. Assuming that the average rental price in that area, for business premises is RM2,000, he is willing to add additional RM582.48⁹ to the rental price for him to fully own the factory in 10 years. Therefore, his total monthly installment would be RM2, 582.48.

⁹ Equation (3) above-mentioned in the Mathematical Derivation for *Musharakah Mutanaqisah* Partnership is used to get this amount of RM582.48.

Table 1: Payments schedule for *mushārahakah mutanāqisah* partnership

Month	Monthly Rent (RM)	Monthly Redemption (RM)	Total Payment (RM)	Customer's Ownership Ratio	Rental Division		IRR = 12.00%		
					Customer	Financier	Customer's Equity (RM)	Financier's Equity (RM)	Financier's Cashflow (RM)
	A	B	C = A + B	D	E	F	G	H	I
0							20000.00	180000.00	(180000.00)
1	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.10000	200.00	1800.00	20782.48	179217.52	2582.48
2	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.10391	207.82	1792.18	21572.78	178427.22	2582.48
3	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.10786	215.73	1784.27	22370.99	177629.01	2582.48
4	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.11185	223.71	1776.29	23177.18	176822.82	2582.48
5	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.11589	231.77	1768.23	23991.43	176008.57	2582.48
6	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.11996	239.91	1760.09	24813.83	175186.17	2582.48
7	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.12407	248.14	1751.86	25644.45	174355.55	2582.48
8	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.12822	256.44	1743.56	26483.37	173516.63	2582.48
9	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.13242	264.83	1735.17	27330.69	172669.31	2582.48
10	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.13665	273.31	1726.69	28186.47	171813.53	2582.48
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
119	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.97456	1949.12	50.88	197443.76	2556.24	2582.48
120	2000	582.48	2582.48	0.98722	1974.44	25.56	200000.67	-0.67	2582.48

5. CONCLUSION

The *mushārahakah mutanāqisah* partnership is a financing instrument available for financing MMEs. The legality of MMP is found in *Qur'an* and *Sunnah* and it is further supported by the consensus of the Muslim *‘ulamā*. This model can be easily applied in various sectors such as housing projects, financing cars purchase, financing working materials and equipments, etc. It has been successfully implemented for house financing in Canada, United States, United Kingdom, Australia, Middle East, Sudan, Pakistan, etc.

Since the MMP consists of several modes of financing (i.e. *mushārahakah*, *ijārah* and *bay’*), its validity lies in implementing the necessary conditions. The main conditions are: (i) these contracts should not be tied-up into a single contract, (ii) the sale of the units of the financier's shares should be carried out at the market value at the time of the sale, and (iii) it should be done through the offer and acceptance.

It has been argued throughout the paper that the MMP, if implemented widely, would have several advantages over the BBA mode of financing as well as conventional loan. The period of financing will be shortened which is beneficial for both, the financier as well as the customer.

In addition to that, this mode would reflect the market movement and the price will never exceed the original price at any point of time. This is not the case with BBA financial technique. The interest rate (*riba*) can be totally avoided and the financier will be less vulnerable to the market movements (Meera and Dzuljastri, 2005).

Unfortunately, the MMP is far from being perfect. It has its own shortcomings, even though, we believe, the advantages of MMP are greater than the shortcomings. The banks may lose some of the profits by implementing MMP, as the customers will pay relatively lower price under this model as shown in the example above, but they may recover some of that loss through the increase in the demand for their services. Furthermore, if we are talking about Islamic banks and their social responsibility then this should not be an obstacle. Current laws and regulations may not be in support of the MMP. Nevertheless, the laws may be amended if there is strong will from the private sector as well as from the government. Determination of the rental prices could create some problems for the bank but it is not a serious one that should keep the banks away from MMP.

Finally, the examples presented in the paper are the best proofs for viability of the MMP. If the various institutions all over the world, even in the west, managed to implement this model successfully then it should not be the problem for the rest of the Islamic banks to do the same. In overall, we can say that the MMP is better solution for the Islamic banks to serve the needs of the Muslim *Ummah*. It is *Shari'ah based* mode of finance accepted internationally.